

Explosion Parameters of SN 2013df and Properties of Its Progenitor Star

A Thesis Presented
by

Diana K. Powell
under the advising of Raffaella Margutti
and Alicia Soderberg

to

The Department of Astronomy

in partial fulfillment of the requirements
for the degree of Bachelor of Arts

April 2014
Harvard University

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Diana Powell

Received _____; accepted _____

ABSTRACT

Type IIb supernovae have only recently been identified as a distinct flavor of core-collapse stellar explosions. These supernovae represent a transitional type between Type II and Type Ib supernovae. Here I present a multi-wavelength (UV-optical) analysis of Type IIb SN 2013df, with the primary goals to (i) constrain the radius of the progenitor star and (ii) determine properties of the stellar explosion. From the analysis of the cooling envelope emission from SN 2013df I constrain the progenitor radius to be $R < 7.8 \times 10^{14}$ cm. I then analyze the main supernova peak that is powered by freshly synthesized ^{56}Ni and find that the total ejecta mass is $M_{ej} = 5.0 M_{\odot}$ and the explosion kinetic energy is $E_k = 3 \times 10^{51}$ erg. Finally, I compare my findings with the explosion and progenitor properties of the currently known and studied sample of Type IIb supernovae from the literature.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Supernovae Explosions

Stellar evolution varies drastically across different stellar types. One of the most important indicators of how a star will evolve is its initial mass. Massive stars ($M > 8M_{\odot}$) end their lives as supernovae. Supernovae have a primary role in the chemical enrichment of our Universe. All heavy chemical elements up to iron were created inside stars and then expelled into the surrounding interstellar medium through supernovae (Smartt 2009). Before a supernova occurs, massive stars burn nuclear fuel in their core to the point that they reach iron (Heger 2012). The process of burning iron no longer gives off the energy required to keep the massive star stable. Thus, the core collapses in a supernova explosion that forms a supernova remnant such as a neutron star or black hole (Heger 2012) (see Figure 1).

Elements heavier than Iron are synthesized during the supernova explosion itself (Smartt 2009). In the case of the core collapse of a massive star, there are two main types of supernovae that can occur, a Type I supernova if the star has lost its hydrogen envelope before exploding or a Type II supernova if the star was able to retain its hydrogen envelope (Heger 2012). The massive star that eventually becomes a supernova is called the *progenitor star*.

Supernovae are among the oldest subject of astronomical research with their discovery dating back to hundreds of years ago. However, it wasn't until the 1930s that supernova

Fig. 1.— A representative diagram of an evolved massive star.

were classified as a specific and unique transient event (Baade & Zwicky 1934). Now the search for new and exotic extragalactic transient events is one of the principle motivations for wide-field astronomy surveys (Kulkarni 2012).

1.2. Modern Research Goals

While supernovae have been studied for many years, there are still basic and important questions that remain to be answered. In particular we would like to understand the relationship between stellar type and type of supernovae explosion. We are now in the position to understand this relationship thanks to:

1. Early capture of supernova explosions
2. Pre-explosion images
3. Multi-wavelength follow-up observations that sample the electromagnetic emission from the X-rays to the radio band

Thanks to recent advances in technology, we are now able to catch supernovae at the time of the explosion. This is incredibly important in furthering our understanding of supernovae because the early data allow us to infer certain properties of the progenitor star such as its radius. Knowledge of the supernova progenitor star is important because it allows for a direct link to be made between the supernova explosions and the progenitors themselves,

thus giving insight into the still uncertain later stages of massive stellar evolution. The observationally derived progenitor and explosion properties can then be used to constrain theoretical predictions of what type of stars produce core-collapse supernovae.

The most direct link between stellar progenitor and explosion properties comes from the detection of the progenitor star in high-resolution pre-explosion images of the supernova site that at the time of writing are only provided by the Hubble Space Telescope (HST). The search for supernovae progenitor stars in high-resolution images started in the 1990s which thus caused telescope archival data to become increasingly important in the field of supernova research. With the current technology for it to be possible to identify the progenitor star of a supernova from pre-explosion images the star must be located in the local Universe (≤ 30 Mpc). This is due to problems of resolution and limiting magnitude (Smartt 2009). In particular, individual massive stars can be resolved out to $\sim 20 - 30$ Mpc using the Hubble Space Telescope and thus the HST has become an invaluable tool for studying pre-explosion images of supernovae progenitor stars (Smartt 2009). In spite of the superb resolution of the HST (1 pixel corresponds to $0.04''$), in these images it is sometimes possible to confuse a compact stellar cluster with a massive star. In some cases, through a combination of spectral-energy distribution (SED), absolute luminosity, and shape analysis the two different objects can be distinguished from each other (Bastian et al. 2005). In the worst cases individual stars cannot be resolved and only a stellar cluster can be identified. However, this finding still provides constraints to the progenitor mass and age. After deriving the colors and luminosity of the progenitor star from these pre-explosion images

we can approximate its location on the Hertzsprung-Russel Diagram (see Figure 2) which can then provide insight into the evolutionary stage of the progenitor before exploding.

The search for a correlation between supernovae and their progenitor stars has yielded some interesting results. Subclasses of Type II supernovae have been associated with stellar progenitors. In particular this has been done for Type IIb (spectroscopically characterized by progressively disappearing Hydrogen features), Type IIc (spectroscopically classified by narrow hydrogen emission lines), and Type IIP (hydrogen-rich explosions characterized by a light curve with a plateau) supernovae. For example, the Type IIP subclass of supernovae has become associated with a population of red supergiant stars (see Figure 2) (Smartt 2009). Very recently, SN 2011dh (a Type IIb supernova) has been associated with a Yellow supergiant progenitor star (see Figure 2) (Soderberg et al. 2012). Another association has been made between a Type IIc supernova (SN 2005gl) and a luminous blue variable (LBV) progenitor star (Gal-Yam et al. 2009). While certain stellar progenitors for Type II supernovae have been found, all of the searches for a progenitor in a pre-explosion image has failed to give a solid detection for a Type I supernova (Eldridge et al. 2013).

The study of supernovae has evolved over time, but it has historically been dominated by optical astronomy (Kulkarni 2012). We can now do a truly multi-wavelength follow up of the explosion, expanding the traditional band of study of supernovae (i.e. optical) to include the non-thermal parts of their spectrum (i.e. radio and X-rays). By modeling the non-thermal emission from supernovae we can accurately constrain information about the mass-loss history of the progenitor star before exploding. The mass-loss in massive star is

Fig. 2.— A representative Hertzsprung-Russell Diagram (H-R diagram) of stars shown as a scatter plot. Progenitors of Type IIP and IIb supernovae have been identified in the supergiant part of the H-R diagram. Image credit: CHANDRA X-ray observatory.

a key but yet not understood parameter in stellar evolution. Coordinated X-ray and radio observations of supernovae explosions can uniquely sample the explosion environment, previously shaped by the progenitor mass-loss.

The study of supernovae explosions is thus timely.

1.3. Introduction to Type IIb Supernovae

The spectroscopic analysis from CBET #3557 (Central Bureau for Astronomical Telegrams) indicates that SN 2013df belongs to the Type IIb supernova subclass so we will therefore concentrate on core-collapse explosions instead of thermonuclear explosions (i.e. Type Ia supernovae). As previously mentioned, Type II supernovae have progenitor stars that are not stripped of their hydrogen envelope, thus distinguishing them from Type I supernovae. Spectroscopically Type IIb supernovae are distinguished from Type II supernovae in that they evolve rapidly so that their spectrum exhibits helium (He) lines while their hydrogen (H) lines weaken and eventually disappear (Smartt 2009). Type IIb supernovae represent an intermediate class between type I and type II Supernovae, as they show evidence for helium and a limited amount of hydrogen in their early-time spectra (hence the Type II classification). The hydrogen, however, later disappears (hence the “b” classification).

Recent discoveries have brought to light the presence of these transitional objects

with rapidly changing spectra (i.e. Type IIb supernova). The identification of this type of object is therefore only possible due to technological advancements that allow us to observe the target at early times. One potential theoretical scenario that describes the evolution of a star to a Type IIb supernova is that a $8 - 17 M_{\odot}$ star in an interacting binary goes supernova and forms a neutron star (See Figure 3) (Smartt 2009). However, there is direct observational evidence that yellow supergiants can form Type IIb supernovae as well (see the discussion below, on SN 2011dh). It is therefore essential that further observations are made on this type of supernova so as to constrain theoretical models.

1.4. Discussion of Research Problem and Solution

The central research problem in the field of core collapse supernovae is the problem of connecting stellar progenitors to the observed properties of their explosions. Essentially, the main goal of characterizing these supernovae is to understand how particular types of stars explode and what types of supernovae they produce. Current theoretical models poorly explain the late stages of stellar evolution leading up to supernovae explosions. This problem has been addressed both theoretically and observationally.

As previously mentioned, one way to attempt to solve this problem is to analyze direct imaging of the explosion site before and after the supernova explosion. The initial observations are crucial but the followup observations are also important as it is often the

Fig. 3.— This diagram shows the theoretical expectations of the evolution of $8 - 10 M_{\odot}$ stars in 2009. According to this, Iib supernovae should arise from interacting binaries. Observations obtained in the last few years proved instead the existence of a completely different evolutionary channel that link Yellow Supergiants with type Iib Supernovae. RSG indicates a Red Supergiant Star and BSG indicates massive Blue Supergiant stars. Image Credit: Smartt 2009

case that the region of explosion contains more than one star. The followup observations allow us to precisely determine which star exploded because that star will have disappeared once the supernova fades as that star will have disappeared from the image. This is almost entirely done using the HST and has only been done for a handful of cases in total. If we restrict the number to just Type IIb explosions then there are two cases of supernovae with pre-explosion images (apart SN 2013df): SN 2008ax and SN 2011dh.

Another extremely important observational tool for understanding the properties of the progenitor star is the application of multi-wavelength modeling of the explosion emission. This can be done in four main ways.

1. Modeling of very early observations: UV-optical emission arising from the cooling of the stellar envelope after the passage of the explosion shock. This phase can last from 1 to a few days, depending on the progenitor size.
2. Modeling optical emission after cooling envelope phase
3. Modeling X-ray observations
4. Modeling radio observations

By modeling very early observations, less than a few days after the explosion, we can track the cooling of the stellar envelope. When a supernova occurs the core collapses which then drives a shock through the stellar envelope that is not yet visible to observers. At a certain point the shock has propagated to a radius that is large enough that the material

between the shock and the observer is transparent to radiation, allowing radiation to propagate to the observer. The observer sees a short (minutes to hour timescales) pulse of radiation known as the supernova shock breakout (Smartt 2009). The shock continues to propagate outwards and heats up the stellar envelope. This produces the “cooling envelope emission”, which dominates on time scales of hours till days after core collapse (Soderberg et al. 2012). This cooling envelope emission is followed by an increase in emission and re-brightening of the supernova due to the radioactive decay of ^{56}Ni on a timescale of approximately a week after the explosion (Arnett 1996). The supernova emission then peaks roughly 2 weeks after the onset of the explosion (Arnett 1996). Modeling of these observations can be used to directly constrain the progenitor radius as the duration and energy of the cooling envelope signal scales with the radius of the progenitor star (Colgate 1974; Ensmann & Burrows 1992; Waxman et al. 2007; Chevalier & Fransson 2008; Katz et al. 2010; Nakar & Sari 2010).

By modeling the optical emission after the cooling envelope phase we can constrain explosion ejecta mass, the amount of nickel produced by the explosion and the explosion kinetic energy (Arnett 1996).

Here, we concentrate on modeling the optical and UV emission from supernovae, however, we provide a brief description of what we can potentially do with our object in the future. By modeling the X-ray observations as inverse Compton scattering we are able to constrain the density of the environment encountered by the explosion shock. Inverse Compton scattering arises from the up scattering of SN optical photons to X-ray energies

by the SN shock. Both Inverse Compton scattering and synchrotron emission allow us to constrain the environment density (and hence the progenitor mass-loss, which is responsible for that material). The advantage of combining X-rays and synchrotron emission is that we will be able to remove the degeneracy between the explosion shock parameters, ϵ_e and ϵ_B . This will allow us to measure how much of the shock energy goes into relativistic electrons (ϵ_e) and how much goes into magnetic field energy (ϵ_B). Both parameters are poorly known. This comparison also gives us the ability to measure the mass-loss from the progenitor star in the decades to years before the explosion.

1.5. Examples of Very Well Studied Type IIb Supernovae

There have only been a few Type IIb supernova that have been well-studied. This is primarily due to the need to classify Type IIb supernovae early enough to catch the variability in their spectra. It is clear from these studies that Type IIb supernovae are a topic of very active research. The five objects discussed below demonstrate how the observations of Type IIb supernovae have evolved with time. They also illustrate how rare and exciting these objects are, especially when given access to a complete dataset with pre-explosion HST images.

1.5.1. *SN 1993J*

SN 1993J in M81 constitutes the first example of a well-studied Type IIb supernova explosion. This is because M81 is a very nearby galaxy ($d = 3.6$ Mpc, Freedman et al. 2001) and thus there were many images in which it was possible to identify the stellar progenitor. This object had a visible cooling envelope characteristic of supernovae that are caught early after they explode (Smartt et al. 2009). Three different theoretical models all predicted that the progenitor star was a member of a binary system that underwent mass transfer (Nomoto et al. 1993, Podsiaklowski et al. 1993, Woosley et al. 1994), however, the exact nature of the stellar progenitor is still actively debated. It took nearly 10 years for the supernova to fade enough for the progenitor star to be uncovered and evidence was then found for a binary system with a B-type and K-type supergiant (Aldering, Humphreys, & Richmond 1994), although the images are not entirely conclusive.

1.5.2. *SN 2008ax*

SN 2008ax was the first Type IIb supernova to be quickly observed in a multi-wavelength study. Roming et al. 2009 came to the conclusion that SN 2008ax had a progenitor that was an unmixed star in an interacting binary. They were also able to determine many of the parameters of the supernova such as mass-loss rate of the progenitor ($\dot{M} = (9 \pm 3) \times 10^{-6} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) (Roming et al. 2009). They were also able to determine

the kinetic energy of the explosion, the ejecta mass, and the nickel mass ($E_k = 0.5 \times 10^{51}$ erg, $M_{ej} = 2.9 M_\odot$, $M_{Ni} = 0.06 M_\odot$) (Roming et al. 2009). Further examination of the pre-explosion images of SN 2008ax indicate that the stellar progenitor was likely a compact source such as a single massive Wolf-Rayet (W-R) star rather than an interacting binary in a low-mass stellar cluster (Crockett et al. 2008). This is significant because it has been theorized that Type IIb supernova are the result of a core collapse in a binary system.

1.5.3. SN 2011dh

SN 2011dh was a part of a comprehensive multi-wavelength study. SN 2011dh was caught early enough that there was data from the cooling envelope emission stage of the supernova (Soderberg et al. 2012). For this supernova, astronomers were able to uncover many of the properties of the stellar progenitor such as the progenitor mass loss rate and the likely progenitor star itself ($\dot{M} \approx 6 \times 10^{-5} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$) (Soderberg et al. 2012). They were in part able to uncover so many characteristics of the progenitor star due to pre-explosion HST images that indicate the supernova progenitor was a yellow supergiant star (Van Dyk et al. 2013). They were also able to uncover many characteristics of the explosion shock such as the shock partition fractions and the time-averaged shock velocity ($(\epsilon_e/\epsilon_B) \sim 30$, $\bar{v} \approx 0.1c$) (Soderberg et al. 2012). This supernova marks the first time that a Type IIb was observed in an early multi-wavelength study with a resolved progenitor star in HST pre-explosion images.

1.5.4. *SN 2011ei*

SN 2011ei was observed in an early multi-wavelength study that well captured the cooling envelope phase of the supernova (Milisavljevic et al. 2013). SN 2011ei was studied in the X-ray, UV/optical, and in the radio. This allowed them to derive many of the same parameters as SN 2011dh ($M_{Ni} = 0.03M_{\odot}$, $M_{ej} = 2.4M_{\odot}$, 2.5×10^{51} erg s⁻¹). While SN 2011ei did not have resolved pre-explosion HST images, they came to a similar conclusion as Crockett et al. 2008 that SN 2011ei has a compact progenitor with a Helium core (Milisavljevic et al. 2013).

1.5.5. *SN 2011hs*

SN 2011hs was observed in a multi-wavelength study spanning a year from X-ray to radio wavelengths (Bufano et al. 2014). This supernova is different from SN 2011ei and similar to SN 2011dh in that its progenitor radius is so large that it indicates the existence of an extended progenitor star ($R \approx 500 - 600 R_{\odot}$) (Bufano et al. 2014). Due to the multi-wavelength nature of the study, Bufano et al. 2014 were able to constrain the same progenitor parameters and shock parameters as SN 2011dh and SN 2011ei ($M_{Ni} \approx 0.04 M_{\odot}$, $E_k = 8.5 \times 10^5$ erg s⁻¹, etc.) (Bufano et al. 2014). However, there is no resolved HST image

for SN 2011hs to further constrain the parameters of the progenitor star.

Thus, there has been a spread of properties of the progenitor stars that have been found including observations that indicate a mixture of binary progenitors, compact progenitors and extended stars. This sample of well studied Type IIb explosions will be used to put SN 2013df into context.

1.6. The Initial Story of SN 2013df

SN 2013df was discovered by F. Ciabattari, E. Mazzoni, S. Donati and G. Petroni in Borgo a Mozzano, Italy on June 7th, 2013. SN 2013df is located at R.A.=12h26m29s.33, Decl.=+31d13'38".3 (J2000). This location is 32" east and 4" north of the center of NGC 4414 which is located 16.9 Mpc away (see Figures 4 and 5). We were able to catch the supernova very early and obtained UVOT and Swift XRT data a mere 3 days after the initial discovery of SN 2013df (see figure 4). Due to quick response times allowing us to observe SN 2013df rapidly after discovery, we were able to observe SN 2013df while its emission was still dominated by the cooling envelope phase. This has been accomplished for very few Type IIb supernovae in the past. We were then able to put together one of the best data sets of a Type IIb explosion ever. This was accomplished through obtaining UV data via Swift UVOT, millimeter data via the Combined Array for Research

in Millimeter-wave Astronomy (CARMA), radio data via the Expanded Very Large Array (EVLA), X-rays via Swift-XRT and Chandra, and spectra via the Multiple Mirror Telescope (MMT). This multi-wavelength data set will enable us to infer the properties of the progenitor star and the properties of the explosion as detailed above. There are also pre-explosion images of the explosion site taken by the Hubble Space Telescope (see figure 5). This means that it will be possible to check which star was the progenitor of this explosion as soon as the supernova has dimmed enough to reveal which star has disappeared.

1.7. Thesis Structure

Here I present multiwavelength (UV to optical) observations of the Type IIb SN 2013df. In Section 2 I discuss the data obtained from the Swift spacecraft. In section 3 I fit the spectral energy distributions (SEDs) with blackbody spectral functions and constrain the progenitor radius. In section 4 I numerically integrate a linear interpolation of the SEDs at each time epoch. In section 5 I use both the blackbody spectral functions and the numerical integrations to calculate the bolometric light curve of SN 2013df. In section 6 I derive the explosion parameters (i.e. ejecta mass M_{ej} and kinetic energy E_K). Conclusions are drawn in Section 7, where I put SN 2013df into the context of other Type IIb explosions.

Fig. 4.— A UV image of SN 2013df. The UV filter w2 onboard the Swift-UVOT tracks the regions of more intense star formation, where SN2013df happened. At this distance, 1 arc minute roughly corresponds to 5 kpc. In this image the blue corresponds to the w2 UVOT filter, the green corresponds to the u filter, and the red corresponds to the v filter. The epoch of this image corresponds to 5 days after the explosion. At this epoch the UV emission in our filters is out-shined by the v-band emission.

Fig. 5.— Hubble Space Telescope image of NGC 4414 taken 1999 Apr 29 with the WFPC2 instrument and F555W filter (equivalent to V-band) through program GO-8400. Box in left panel highlights enlarged region around SN 2013df shown in right panel. A circle of diameter 0.75'' outlines three candidate progenitor stars that fall within the the total positional uncertainty of coordinates $RA(J2000.0) = 12h26m29.35s$ $DEC(J2000.0) = +31d13m37.5s$ (van Dyk et al. 2013, ATel 5139). Data reduction and image curtesy of D. Milisavljevic

2. Data

SN 2013df was observed using swift UVOT in six different filters (bb, vv, uu, w1, m2, w2). These filters span the UV and much of the optical (see Figure 6). Swift UVOT data have been reduced using HEASOFT v6.14 and corresponding calibration files. The data from Swift UVOT was corrected for extinction from the Milky Way along the line of sight ($A_v = 0.053$ mag Schlafly & Finkbeiner 2011) as well as corrected from extinction from the host galaxy calculated from a high quality spectra of the supernova. From our spectrum acquired on Nov 8th we measure negligible extinction (from the NaD absorption line, see Poznanski et al. 2012) in the host galaxy, hence we assume $A_v = 0$ for the host. The data were also subtracted from background contamination from the host galaxy.

2.1. UVOT Lightcurves

Tables 1-6 give the final extinction corrected and background subtracted photometry of SN 2013df. There were 19 different epochs of observation starting at 56450.87 MJD. Figure 7 shows a plot of the multi band photometry of SN 2013df. The initial decrease in the flux of each light curve followed by an increase in emission is indicative of the cooling envelope phase of Type IIb supernovae when caught early on.

Fig. 6.— A plot of the filter passbands for Swift-UVOT. Here the three UV filters, UVW1, UVM2, and UVW2 are referred to in the paper as w1, m2, and w2.

Days Since Explosion	B-band Flux (erg/s/cm ² /Å)	B-band Error
5.6	6.13×10^{-15}	2.11×10^{-16}
8.0	4.10×10^{-15}	1.59×10^{-16}
8.9	4.09×10^{-15}	1.70×10^{-16}
12.4	4.21×10^{-15}	1.69×10^{-16}
14.9	4.59×10^{-15}	1.90×10^{-16}
16.5	4.47×10^{-15}	1.73×10^{-16}
18.2	4.86×10^{-15}	1.93×10^{-16}
22.5	3.32×10^{-15}	1.47×10^{-16}
24.6	2.60×10^{-15}	1.25×10^{-16}
26.8	1.84×10^{-15}	1.17×10^{-16}
28.5	1.60×10^{-15}	1.06×10^{-16}
30.5	1.09×10^{-15}	9.59×10^{-17}
32.9	8.68×10^{-16}	9.14×10^{-17}
35.0	7.09×10^{-16}	9.85×10^{-17}
36.3	6.99×10^{-16}	8.97×10^{-17}
38.5	5.95×10^{-16}	9.45×10^{-17}
45.4	5.03×10^{-16}	7.35×10^{-17}
49.7	4.27×10^{-16}	9.59×10^{-17}
53.4	2.95×10^{-16}	7.64×10^{-17}

Table 1: This table shows the extinction corrected and background subtracted measurements for flux density in the UVOT B-band of SN 2013df with the corresponding errors.

Days Since Explosion	V-band Flux (erg/s/cm ² /Å)	V-band Error
5.6	4.92×10^{-15}	1.78×10^{-16}
8.0	3.63×10^{-15}	1.73×10^{-16}
8.9	3.63×10^{-15}	1.83×10^{-16}
12.4	4.33×10^{-15}	1.93×10^{-16}
14.9	5.36×10^{-15}	2.38×10^{-16}
16.5	5.80×10^{-15}	2.93×10^{-16}
18.2	5.26×10^{-15}	2.28×10^{-16}
22.5	4.74×10^{-15}	2.06×10^{-16}
24.6	3.98×10^{-15}	1.82×10^{-16}
26.8	3.27×10^{-15}	1.82×10^{-16}
28.5	2.72×10^{-15}	1.60×10^{-16}
30.5	2.21×10^{-15}	1.49×10^{-16}
32.9	1.69×10^{-15}	1.75×10^{-16}
35.0	1.77×10^{-15}	1.59×10^{-16}
36.3	1.66×10^{-15}	1.40×10^{-16}
38.5	1.06×10^{-15}	1.50×10^{-16}
45.4	1.12×10^{-15}	1.06×10^{-16}
49.7	1.16×10^{-15}	1.50×10^{-16}
53.4	8.88×10^{-16}	1.12×10^{-16}

Table 2: This table shows the extinction corrected and background subtracted measurements for flux density in the UVOT v-band of SN 2013df with the corresponding errors.

Days Since Explosion	U-band Flux (erg/s/cm ² /Å)	U-band Error
5.6	7.39×10^{-15}	2.67×10^{-16}
8.0	4.12×10^{-15}	1.72×10^{-16}
8.9	3.74×10^{-15}	1.70×10^{-16}
12.4	3.39×10^{-15}	1.50×10^{-16}
14.9	2.80×10^{-15}	1.35×10^{-16}
16.5	2.68×10^{-15}	1.41×10^{-16}
18.2	2.37×10^{-15}	1.20×10^{-16}
22.5	2.23×10^{-15}	1.23×10^{-16}
24.6	1.53×10^{-15}	9.84×10^{-17}
26.8	1.15×10^{-15}	8.41×10^{-17}
28.5	7.79×10^{-16}	8.21×10^{-17}
30.5	4.57×10^{-16}	6.94×10^{-17}
32.9	4.71×10^{-16}	7.15×10^{-17}
35.0	3.26×10^{-16}	6.52×10^{-17}
36.3	2.83×10^{-16}	7.57×10^{-17}
38.5	2.33×10^{-16}	6.73×10^{-17}
45.4	1.94×10^{-16}	6.08×10^{-17}
49.7	8.34×10^{-17}	5.47×10^{-17}
53.4	1.31×10^{-16}	7.31×10^{-17}

Table 3: This table shows the extinction corrected and background subtracted measurements for flux density in the UVOT U-band of SN 2013df with the corresponding errors.

Days Since Explosion	W1-band Flux (erg/s/cm ² /Å)	W1-band Error
5.6	5.41×10^{-15}	2.42×10^{-16}
8.0	2.66×10^{-15}	1.46×10^{-16}
8.9	2.66×10^{-15}	1.47×10^{-16}
12.4	1.90×10^{-15}	1.14×10^{-16}
14.9	1.88×10^{-15}	1.21×10^{-16}
16.5	1.65×10^{-15}	1.03×10^{-16}
18.2	1.47×10^{-15}	1.03×10^{-16}
22.5	1.20×10^{-15}	9.06×10^{-17}
24.6	8.85×10^{-16}	7.75×10^{-17}
26.8	7.76×10^{-16}	8.12×10^{-17}
28.5	6.88×10^{-16}	7.51×10^{-17}
30.5	5.04×10^{-16}	7.04×10^{-17}
32.9	3.84×10^{-16}	6.16×10^{-17}
35.0	4.37×10^{-16}	7.62×10^{-17}
36.3	3.45×10^{-16}	6.68×10^{-17}
38.5	3.40×10^{-16}	6.25×10^{-17}
45.4	2.36×10^{-16}	5.48×10^{-17}
49.7	1.60×10^{-16}	5.90×10^{-17}
53.4	1.26×10^{-16}	5.60×10^{-17}

Table 4: This table shows the extinction corrected and background subtracted measurements for flux density in the UVOT W1-band of SN 2013df with the corresponding errors.

Days Since Explosion	M2-band Flux (erg/s/cm ² /Å)	M2-band Error
5.6	3.84×10^{-15}	1.82×10^{-16}
8.0	1.84×10^{-15}	1.12×10^{-16}
8.9	1.57×10^{-15}	9.42×10^{-17}
12.4	1.04×10^{-15}	8.15×10^{-17}
14.9	1.00×10^{-15}	7.06×10^{-17}
16.5	1.09×10^{-15}	7.86×10^{-17}
18.2	9.54×10^{-16}	8.60×10^{-17}
22.5	7.97×10^{-16}	6.63×10^{-17}
24.6	5.84×10^{-16}	5.62×10^{-17}
26.8	5.63×10^{-16}	6.29×10^{-17}
28.5	4.20×10^{-16}	5.45×10^{-17}
30.5	3.11×10^{-16}	4.76×10^{-17}
32.9	3.31×10^{-16}	4.93×10^{-17}
35.0	1.54×10^{-16}	5.47×10^{-17}
36.3	1.98×10^{-16}	5.05×10^{-17}
38.5	2.04×10^{-16}	4.83×10^{-17}
45.4	1.68×10^{-16}	5.43×10^{-17}
49.7	1.13×10^{-16}	3.71×10^{-17}
53.4	1.69×10^{-16}	5.52×10^{-17}

Table 5: This table shows the extinction corrected and background subtracted measurements for flux density in the UVOT M2-band of SN 2013df with the corresponding errors.

Days Since Explosion	W2-band Flux (erg/s/cm ² /Å)	W2-band Error
5.6	3.26×10^{-15}	2.04×10^{-16}
8.0	1.44×10^{-15}	1.17×10^{-16}
8.9	1.35×10^{-15}	1.15×10^{-16}
12.4	9.60×10^{-16}	9.86×10^{-17}
14.9	8.88×10^{-16}	1.07×10^{-16}
16.5	1.01×10^{-15}	1.25×10^{-16}
18.2	7.92×10^{-16}	8.85×10^{-17}
22.5	7.20×10^{-16}	9.06×10^{-17}
24.6	6.22×10^{-16}	8.63×10^{-17}
26.8	5.64×10^{-16}	8.23×10^{-17}
28.5	3.84×10^{-16}	7.33×10^{-17}
30.5	2.33×10^{-16}	6.67×10^{-17}
32.9	1.16×10^{-16}	6.75×10^{-17}
35.0	8.78×10^{-17}	6.47×10^{-17}
36.3	9.50×10^{-17}	6.55×10^{-17}
38.5	–	–
45.4	8.98×10^{-18}	6.87×10^{-17}
49.7	4.31×10^{-17}	6.53×10^{-17}
53.4	–	–

Table 6: This table shows the extinction corrected and background subtracted measurements for flux density in the UVOT W2-band of SN 2013df with the corresponding errors.

Fig. 7.— Plot of multi-band photometry of SN 2013df. This data has undergone a preliminary correction for extinction and emission from the host galaxy. A more careful calculation can only be performed when the emission from SN 2013df fades away. Each curve represents a different filter from Swift UVOT. The dashed line indicates when emission changes from being cooling envelope dominated to ⁵⁶Ni decay dominated.

3. Blackbody Approximations and Constraint on the Progenitor Radius

The progenitor radius of a Type IIb supernova can be constrained through modeling the spectral energy distributions (SEDs) with a black-body spectral function at early times. This model gives a value of the radius of the ejection material which can then be used to constrain the radius of the progenitor star.

3.1. Modeling the SEDs

The spectral energy distribution (SED) of a supernova can give important insight into the properties of the ejecta material (namely ejecta radius and temperature). At early times, the SED can be modeled with a black-body function. A spectral energy distribution can be modeled by the Planck function to determine the properties of the ejection material.

The Planck function is:

$$B_\lambda(T) = \frac{2hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{hc}{\lambda k_B T}} - 1} \quad (1)$$

where B is the spectral radiance, h is planck’s constant, c is the speed of light, and k_B is Boltzmann’s constant. The Planck function can be used to obtain the flux density for an object of a particular radius r at a distance D , therefore calculating the flux density, as follows:

$$S_\lambda = \frac{B_\lambda \times r^2 \pi}{D^2} \quad (2)$$

The position of the peak of the Planck function is directly linked to the temperature of the emission, with the Plank function peaking at shorter wavelengths for higher

temperatures. For a given temperature, the amount of flux at each wavelength scales with the radius of the emitting region (i.e. the blackbody radius in this case). The SEDs were each modeled using least-squares minimization in IDL to obtain the Planck function that is the most similar to the observed SED. The best-fit in least-squares minimization minimizes the sum of the square of the residuals.

3.2. SED Evolution with Time

The Spectral Energy Distribution (SED) of a supernova changes with time as the ejecta material expands and cools. For Type IIb supernovae the SEDs roughly resemble a blackbody distribution at early times (see Figure 8). This is because the ejecta of a supernova is dense enough at early times that the radiating photons are thermalized. A perfect blackbody is a body that emits all of the heat that it absorbs. Even at very early times, deviations from a pure black-body spectrum are expected. However, a blackbody gives a reasonable fit to the first 4 epochs (see Figure 3), allowing us to put firm constraints to the progenitor radius. Overtime the SED of SN 2013df changes drastically. Using Swift UVOT data there are 19 different epochs of data that comprise 19 SEDs with six data points corresponding to each Swift UVOT filter. With time the peak of the blackbody curve shifts towards longer wavelengths, indicating a decrease in the temperature of the ejecta. For SN 2013df a blackbody approximation can only be used for the first four observation dates (See Figure 9). After this point the ejecta is too diffuse to thermalize the photons.

For times after the first four observation dates the blackbody approximation does not work. This is due to the much more diffuse ejecta that probes a different temperature and radius because the photons can no longer be thermalized. An example of an attempted SED model for later times is shown in Figure 10. It is clear that the blackbody approximation does not hold even when only fitting the last three data points.

Fig. 8.— Each curve represents a classical blackbody curve. The peak emission increases as the blackbody temperature increases. The wavelength at which a blackbody peaks corresponds to the part of the electromagnetic spectrum that contains the majority of the object’s emission.

Fig. 9.— These figures show the modeled SEDs for the first four observation dates. At this time the escaping photons are thermalized, thus giving off emission that can be modeled by a blackbody. The model shows good agreement with the data (see tables 7-9 for more details).

Fig. 10.— A representation of a poor blackbody SED fit at later time epochs of the supernova observation. Only the longest three data points are incorporated in the fit.

3.3. Ejecta Temperature and Radius Evolution with Time

The temperature of the ejecta changes as the explosion material cools and expands (see Table 7 and Figure 11). There is a marked and steady decrease in the temperature of the ejecta with time. The radius of the ejecta increases with time as the material expands into the interstellar medium (see Table 8 and Figure 12). These two plots roughly follow a power law evolution. The power law for each plot was again found through a least squares minimization technique.

3.4. Upper Limit on the Progenitor Radius

Thus, the first data point is the point in which the material has expanded the least. This means that we can take our earliest estimate of the ejecta radius as an upper-limit on the radius of the progenitor star. Therefore, our upper limit on the radius of the progenitor star is 7.8×10^{14} cm. This is larger than any known large star and thus does not drastically narrow down the potential progenitor star.

Days Since Explosion	Temperature (K)	1- σ Temperature Error (K)
5.6	8330	80
8.0	7628	90
8.9	7439	80
12.4	6654	80

Table 7: This table shows the values for the best-fit blackbody temperatures as determined through a least squares fitting routine as well as the $1 - \sigma$ error on these values.

Fig. 11.— A plot of the evolution of the temperature of the supernova ejecta with time. The red line represents the best power law fit to the data.

Days Since Explosion	Ejecta Radius (cm)	1- σ Radius Error (cm)
5.6	7.8×10^{14}	2.1×10^{13}
8.0	7.5×10^{14}	2.5×10^{13}
8.9	7.8×10^{14}	2.8×10^{13}
12.4	1.0×10^{15}	3.9×10^{13}

Table 8: This table shows the values for the best-fit blackbody radius as determined through a least squares fitting routine as well as the $1 - \sigma$ error on these values.

Fig. 12.— A plot of the evolution of the Radius of the supernova ejecta with time. The red line represents the best power law fit to the data.

3.5. Blackbody Luminosity

The blackbody function can be used to give a flux density value. Integrating under this flux density then gives us a total value for the flux which can be converted to a value for luminosity using the following equation:

$$L = 4\pi D^2 S_\lambda \quad (3)$$

Where D is the luminosity distance (16.9 Mpc for SN 2013df) and F is the total flux. The blackbody luminosity and errors are given in Table 9.

The error for the blackbody luminosity can be derived as follows. For a blackbody of radius R and temperature T , the luminosity is $L = 4\pi R^2 \sigma T^4$ where σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant. The total error on the blackbody luminosity would then be:

$$\sigma_L = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial R}\right)^2 \sigma_R^2 + \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial T}\right)^2 \sigma_T^2 + \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial R}\right) \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial T}\right) \sigma_{TR}} \quad (4)$$

Here we assume that the two variables are independent and therefore we can approximate the error on the luminosity simply as follows:

$$\sigma_L = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial R}\right)^2 \sigma_R^2 + \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial T}\right)^2 \sigma_T^2} \quad (5)$$

Days Since Explosion	Luminosity (erg/s)	Luminosity Error
5.6	2.09×10^{42}	1.38×10^{41}
8.0	1.35×10^{42}	2.06×10^{41}
8.9	1.33×10^{42}	2.61×10^{41}
12.4	1.40×10^{42}	2.66×10^{41}

Table 9: This table shows the values for the best-fit blackbody luminosity

4. Numerical Integration of the SEDs

At early times (first four observation dates) we are able to model the SEDs with a blackbody curve because the ejecta is dense enough to thermalize the escaping photons. However, past these first four observation dates the ejecta becomes diffuse and the emission becomes non thermal as the photons can no longer be thermalized by the ejecta material. This later emission is thus probing from the inside of the supernova remnant powered by ^{56}Ni and does not give physical parameters when modeled with a blackbody curve.

However, it is possible to obtain a bolometric light curve without the use of blackbody curves. To do this, I use a linear interpolation for every SED (see Figure 13). The linear interpolation connects the 6 different values of the SED and returns values for the points in between each observationally derived data point. This interpolation then allowed me to calculate the area under the curve through integration via a trapezoidal rule. This integral gives a value of the total flux which can then be converted to a value for the bolometric luminosity.

To calculate the error for this curve I utilized the $1-\sigma$ uncertainties on the measurements

of the data points and calculate the area under the curve accounting for error in individual data points. I did this for both the upper and lower 1- σ errors. The error bars seen on the bolometric light curve are therefore the error is:

$$Final\ Luminosity \pm \left(\frac{L_3 - L_2}{2} \right) \quad (6)$$

where L_3 is the bolometric luminosity calculated with the addition of the 1- σ error and L_2 is the bolometric luminosity calculated with the subtraction of the 1- σ error (see Figure 14).

The linear interpolation does not give an approximate value for the areas that are not in our wavelength range unlike the model of the blackbody curve that incorporates flux at all wavelengths. Thus, we obtain a pseudo-bolometric light curve through the linear interpolation technique. However, the pseudo-bolometric light curve is still suitable for our main research goals as discussed further in the following sections.

5. The Bolometric Lightcurve of SN 2013df

A bolometric light curve is a plot of the integrated flux as a function of time that gives a measure of the total radiated energy of a supernova (Smartt 2009). The bolometric light curve of a supernova can give insight into the energy evolution of the supernova explosion. To create the bolometric light curve of SN 2013df using the blackbody fits previously derived for the first four time epochs I used the following equation with my fitted values for radius and temperature:

$$L = 4\pi R^2 \sigma T^4 \quad (7)$$

Fig. 13.— An example of a linearly interpolated SED. The area was calculated under the curve to derive a value for psuedo-bolometric luminosity.

Fig. 14.— An example of a linearly interpolated SED with dashed lines connecting the $1 - \sigma$ error bars. To calculate error for the linearly interpolated SED I calculated the area under the dashed blue line and converted this value to luminosity L_3 and the dashed green line L_2 and used the average of these values as the error.

where σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant. These values for luminosity give a complete bolometric light curve for the first four time epochs (see figure 15).

Fig. 15.— A plot of the bolometric light curve of SN 2013df for the first four time epochs. This bolometric light curve is complete in that it accounts for the entirety of the flux from the supernovae at these times. This is because these luminosity values are derived from the best-fit blackbody function which provides an estimate for the total flux across all wavelengths.

For times after the first four observation points I integrated under the linear interpolation of the SED and converted this value for total flux to luminosity using equation (3). Using this method there is missing flux unaccounted for in the value for luminosity.

This is frequently corrected for using a time evolved correction factor, however, it is possible to accurately constrain certain explosion properties without this correction factor with the use of a pseudo-bolometric light curve.

The pseudo bolometric light curve can be seen in Figure 16. The points of this light curve are the values derived from the integration of the linear interpolation of the SED. The luminosity values for each time can be found in Table 10.

The bolometric light curve represents the sum of each individual filter light curve. Thus, there is evidence of a cooling envelope present in this light curve as well as in many of the individual filter light curves. However, the cooling envelope phase is not quite as pronounced as it is in some of the individual UVOT filters (i.e. bb, vv).

6. Derivation of Explosion Parameters

Through modeling the bolometric light curve it is possible to determine the explosion parameters of the supernova, such as ejecta mass M_{ej} and the kinetic energy of the explosion E_K .

6.1. Modeling of Bolometric Lightcurve

There are three different parts of the bolometric light curve that can typically be modeled for type IIb supernovae: the cooling envelope phase, the photospheric phase, and the nebular phase. The cooling envelope phase occurs very early in the life of a supernova

Fig. 16.— A plot of the bolometric light curve of SN 2013df. There is evidence of a cooling envelope in that the luminosity appears to initially decline while then plateauing before dramatically decreasing. These values for luminosity are derived from the integration of the linear interpolation of the SEDs. Thus, there is missing flux left unaccounted for which is why this is a pseudo bolometric light curve instead of a complete light curve that accounts for all of the flux from the supernova.

Days Since Explosion	Interpolated Luminosity (erg/s)	Error (erg/s)
5.6	6.62×10^{41}	7.42×10^{40}
8.0	3.98×10^{41}	4.09×10^{40}
8.9	3.69×10^{41}	3.82×10^{40}
12.4	3.37×10^{41}	3.72×10^{40}
14.9	5.16×10^{41}	3.77×10^{40}
16.5	5.13×10^{41}	3.69×10^{40}
18.2	4.96×10^{41}	3.64×10^{40}
22.5	3.99×10^{41}	2.80×10^{40}
24.6	3.09×10^{41}	2.03×10^{40}
26.8	2.39×10^{41}	1.29×10^{40}
28.5	1.95×10^{41}	9.10×10^{39}
30.5	1.39×10^{41}	3.97×10^{39}
32.9	1.14×10^{41}	7.76×10^{38}
35.0	1.02×10^{41}	7.73×10^{38}
36.3	9.50×10^{40}	8.79×10^{38}
38.5	7.40×10^{40}	3.08×10^{39}
45.4	6.58×10^{40}	2.14×10^{39}
49.7	5.63×10^{40}	4.69×10^{39}
53.4	4.70×10^{40}	4.95×10^{39}

Table 10: This table shows the values for luminosity derived from the interpolated SEDs.

($t \leq 10$ days) and is thus only seen in supernovae that are caught very early on. The photospheric phase is longer than the cooling envelope phase and typically occurs $t \leq 30$ days. The nebular phase is that last supernova phase that is typically modeled and it occurs at $t \geq 60$ days past the explosion. The model that we discuss is the model from Valenti et al. 2008 that models both the photospheric and nebular phase of supernovae. For SN 2013df we will concentrate on modeling the photospheric phase of the bolometric light curve to derive the explosion parameters.

6.1.1. *Basic Principles of Modeling Photospheric Phase*

While precise relations have been found to model the photospheric phase of the supernova light curve, it is possible to understand the underlying principles of the model with a knowledge of basic physics. The model can be roughly derived starting with the first law of thermodynamics:

$$\frac{dE}{dt} + P \frac{dV}{dt} = -\frac{dL}{dm} + \epsilon \quad (8)$$

where E is the internal energy per unit mass, P is the pressure, V is the specific volume $1/\rho$, L is the radiative luminosity, m is the spherical mass coordinate, and ϵ is the radioactive heating due to the decay of ^{56}Ni (dissipation of energy by γ -rays).

The first law of thermodynamics can then be used to derive relations for our explosion parameters (ejecta mass M_{ej} , kinetic energy E_k , and nickel mass M_{Ni}) after making the following assumptions:

1. Homologous expansion in spherical symmetry
2. Dominated by radiation pressure ($P = aT^4$)
3. ^{56}Ni present in the ejected matter
4. ^{56}Ni distributed in the center of the ejecta
5. An optical opacity $k_{opt} = 0.05$

Applying these assumptions to the first law of thermodynamics gives the following relations:

$$\left(\frac{\tau_c}{days}\right) \approx \frac{8(M_{ej}/m_\odot)^{3/4}}{(E_k/10^{51}erg)^{1/4}} \quad (9)$$

which is the width of the light curve.

$$M_{ej} \approx 0.8 \left(\frac{\tau_c}{8 days}\right)^2 \left(\frac{V_{ph}}{10,000 km/s}\right) M_\odot \quad (10)$$

$$\left(\frac{E_k}{10^{51}erg}\right) \approx 0.5 \left(\frac{\tau_c}{8 days}\right)^2 \left(\frac{V_{ph}}{10000 km/s}\right) \quad (11)$$

Where V_{ph} is the photospheric velocity. Together, these relations constrain the ejecta mass and explosion kinetic energy

6.2. Model of SN 2013df

To obtain the explosion parameters of SN 2013df I modeled the photospheric phase of the supernova light curve (See Figure 17). This was done using the model from Valenti et

al. 2008 as described in the appendix of the 2008 paper. However, this fit to the supernova is less than ideal due to degeneracies in the more complex model. Thus, when adopting my values for the explosion parameters I estimate the ejecta mass and explosion kinetic energy using the two scaling relations above, which are derived from the model of Valenti et al.

2008.

Fig. 17.— A plot of the modeled bolometric light curve of SN 2013df. The photospheric phase of the supernovae roughly lies between the two dashed black lines ($10 \geq t \leq 30$). The red points represented the derived bolometric light curve while the blue line represents the best fit model derived using the scaling relations from Valenti et al. 2008.

6.3. Explosion Parameters

Through the use of the scaling relations in section 5.1.1, approximating the light curve width to be ~ 20 days and the V_{ph} to be $\sim 10,000$ km/s we obtain different explosion parameters that we will use for the time being. The width of the light curve is approximated through an analysis of the bolometric light curve (see Figure 16). This rough estimate is used because further accuracy requires the addition of the missing flux to the pseudo bolometric light curve. In the future we plan to correct for this missing flux with the addition of further photometry. The value of 10,000 km/s is an approximate value for the photospheric velocity that is commonly found in the literature. Through this approximate method I find: $M_{ej} = 5 M_{\odot}$, and $E_k = 3 \times 10^{51}$ erg s $^{-1}$. I will adopt these values for the remainder of the paper. Here we do not discuss the error on these values because they are extremely rough calculations. This follows the trend for papers on Type IIb supernovae in which the errors on these values are not reported in the published papers.

7. Conclusions and Context

SN 2013df is one of the few Type IIb supernovae in which we have been able to actively constrain both parameters of the explosion and of the progenitor star. SN 2013df shows several similarities and differences to other objects in the Type IIb supernova subclass. Due to the small number of Type IIb supernovae that have been studied in depth, it

is especially important to put SN 2013df in the context of other Type IIb explosions. This contextualization can then lead to observational conclusions of the entire Type IIb supernova subclass.

7.1. Progenitor Radius Constraints

Five other Type IIb supernovae in particular have fairly constrained progenitor radii (SN 1993j, SN 2008ax, SN 2011dh, SN 2011hs, SN 2011ei) (see Figure 18). The constraint on the radius of SN 2013df is the largest radius of a Type IIb supernova yet found. This is likely due to catching the supernova early enough to see the cooling envelope phase but not early enough to tightly constrain the progenitor radius due to the rapid expansion of the ejecta material. The radius of SN 2013df can be further constrained through two different ways. The first of which is to model the cooling envelope phase of the bolometric light curve and use this model to relate the cooling envelope phase with the progenitor star. Another way to further constrain the radius of the progenitor star is through photometry on the HST pre-explosion images of SN 2013df. Through this photometry, we could obtain the spectral type of the three candidate stars and determine their approximate radii.

7.2. Bolometric Light Curve Comparisons

I also compare the pseudo bolometric light curve of SN 2013df to the five previously mentioned Type IIb supernovae (see Figure 19). The light curves are all a function

Fig. 18.— A plot of the constraints on the radii of the progenitor star of several type IIb supernovae. Values with an arrow instead of an error bar represent an upper limit to the progenitor radius. These radii are taken from the following papers: Smartt 2009, Crockett et al. 2008, Soderberg et al. 2012, Bufano et al. 2014, Milisavljevic et al. 2013.

of the time since explosion. Each of the six light curves vary somewhat in the overall bolometric luminosity with the early Type IIb’s having higher luminosity than those Type IIb supernovae discovered more recently. The peak luminosity of a bolometric light curve gives insight into the amount of ^{56}Ni produced in an explosion (Bufano et al. 2014). Thus, the explosions with a lower peak luminosity have a lower amount of ^{56}Ni in the ejected material.

Nearly all of the light curves have a dominant peak of nearly the same wide shape with a dramatic decline after the peak. However, the early stages of the light curves are fairly different from each other. Three of the six Type IIb supernovae shown show evidence of a sharp decline at the onset of their light curves followed by an increase towards the wide peak seen in all of the light curves. SN 1993j and SN 2011hs have light curves that show very clear signs of cooling envelope evolution. SN 2013df also shows signs of a cooling envelope phase that was detected by the instruments on Swift UVOT.

The width of a bolometric light curve gives insight into the ratio of ejecta mass and explosion kinetic energy, with ”lighter” ejecta and more energetic explosions being associated to supernovae with narrower peaks following Arnett’s relation for which $\tau_{peak} \propto M_{ej}^{3/4} E_k^{-1/4}$. For the Type IIb supernovae compared here, the peaks are roughly the same width. However, SN 2011hs and SN 2013df appear to have a narrower light curve than other type IIb supernovae, indicating that the ratio of M_{ej} to E_k is smaller than in the other supernovae.

Fig. 19.— A plot of the bolometric light curves of SN 2013df, SN 2011ei, SN 2011hs, SN 1993j, SN 2008ax, and SN 2011dh. The light curves for the other supernovae were taken from Bufano et al. 2014 and Milisavljevic et al. 2013. The light curves are all normalized so that they start at the same date (the date of the estimated supernovae explosion).

7.3. Comparison of Explosion Parameters

There are three typically studied supernovae explosion parameters (M_{ej} , E_k , and M_{Ni}). These parameters give insight into the mechanisms that take place in a supernovae explosion. The explosion parameters that I derived for SN 2013df can thus be compared to the explosion parameters derived for other Type IIb explosions (see Figures 20 and 21). No immediate conclusions or trends arise from a comparison of the different supernovae explosion parameters for these Type IIb stellar explosions.

Fig. 20.— A plot of the M_{ej} versus the M_{Ni} for three Type IIb supernovae. There is no clear trend present in the data. The four supernovae have similar M_{Ni} but are more spread in the M_{ej} .

Fig. 21.— A plot of E_k versus the M_{ej} for four Type IIb supernovae. There is no clear trend present in the data.

8. Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my amazing and helpful advisers Raffaella Margutti and Alicia Soderberg as well as the incredibly supportive members of the Soderberg group: Dan Milisavljevic, Nathan Sanders and Maria Drout. I would also like to thank the other students in Astro 99, Prof. Jim Moran, the Harvard College Department of Astronomy, and my lifelong fans Raina Gandhi and Faith Deis. Of course I would also like to thank my ever supportive family.

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